

1 **Extracellular pH controls chemotaxis of neutrophil**
2 **granulocytes by regulating LTB₄ production and**
3 **Cdc42 signaling**

4 Running title: pH regulates neutrophil chemotaxis

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25 **Keywords: neutrophil, pH, chemotaxis, NHE1, leukotriene B₄, Cdc42**

26 **Abstract**

27 Neutrophil granulocytes are the first and robust responders to the chemotactic molecules
28 released from an inflamed, acidic tissue. The aim of this study was to elucidate the role
29 of the microenvironmental pH in neutrophil chemotaxis. To this end, we combined live
30 cell imaging chemotaxis assays with measurements of the intracellular pH (pH_i) in
31 varied extracellular pH (pH_e). Observational studies were complemented by
32 biochemical analyses of leukotriene B_4 production and activation of the Cdc42 Rho
33 GTPase. Our data show that pH_i of neutrophils dose-dependently adapts to a given pH
34 of the extracellular milieu. Neutrophil chemotaxis towards C5a has an optimum at
35 $\text{pH}_i \sim 7.1$ and its pH_i dependency is almost parallel to that of LTB_4 production.
36 Consequently, a shallow pH_e gradient, resembling that encountered by neutrophils
37 during extravasation from a blood vessel ($\text{pH} \sim 7.4$) into the interstitium ($\text{pH} \sim 7.2$), favors
38 chemotaxis of stimulated neutrophils. Lowering pH_e below $\text{pH} 6.8$, predominantly
39 affects neutrophil chemotaxis, while the velocity is largely maintained. Inhibition of the
40 Na^+/H^+ -exchanger 1 (NHE1) with cariporide drastically attenuates neutrophil
41 chemotaxis at the optimal pH_i irrespective of the high LTB_4 production. Neutrophil
42 migration/chemotaxis is almost completely abrogated by inhibiting LTB_4 production or
43 blocking its receptor (BLT1). The abundance of the active GTP-bound form of Cdc42 is
44 strongly reduced by NHE1 inhibition or $\text{pH}_e 6.5$. In conclusion, we propose that the pH
45 dependence of neutrophil chemotaxis towards C5a is caused by a pH_i -dependent
46 production of LTB_4 and activation of Cdc42. Moreover, it requires the activity of the
47 Na^+/H^+ exchanger NHE1.

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50 **Key points:**

51 Neutrophil chemotaxis towards C5a depends on intra- and extracellular pH.

52 pH controls LTB₄ secretion and Cdc42 activation.

53 Chemotaxis requires the activity of the Na⁺/H⁺ exchanger NHE1.

54 **1 Introduction**

55 Neutrophil granulocytes are the first immune cells to arrive at a site of inflammation.
56 Guided by chemoattractants, they extravasate and migrate towards affected sites to
57 deploy their defense mechanisms (1). Robust neutrophil effector functions help to fight
58 against invading pathogens, but inadequate neutrophil response can also be harmful for
59 the host. In severe inflammation, dysfunctional neutrophils can impede the activity of
60 other cells of the innate and adaptive immunity (2). Recently, neutrophil dysfunction
61 was shown to contribute to thrombotic events in COVID-19 patients (3).

62 The inflammatory microenvironment often acidifies because of the lactate release,
63 tissue oxygen deprivation and primarily glycolytic metabolism of the arriving
64 neutrophils (4). Production of reactive oxygen and nitrogen species (ROS, RNS) during
65 the respiratory burst of neutrophils leads to an H^+ efflux mediated by H^+ channels and in
66 part by the Na^+/H^+ exchanger NHE1. Thus, increased neutrophil activity adds to the
67 acidification of the inflammatory microenvironment (5, 6, 7) which in turn will also
68 affect the intracellular pH of neutrophils.

69 It is known that low pH_e elicits either pro- or anti-inflammatory effects. For instance,
70 NETosis, one of the major defense mechanisms of neutrophils, is inhibited by the
71 acidity (8). An acidic environment also prolongs the survival of neutrophils (4). The
72 remarkable ability of neutrophils to survive in an acidic, oxygen- and glucose-deprived
73 environment, which is characteristic for autoimmune diseases, chronic inflammation
74 and solid tumors, often leads to unfavorable neutrophil dysfunction and retention.
75 Neutrophil activity thereby often contributes to the burden of the above mentioned
76 conditions (9, 10). The acidic pH of the inflammatory microenvironment may influence
77 neutrophil chemotaxis in a dual way - render neutrophils unable to reach the site of

78 inflammation or, on the contrary, cause excessive neutrophil accumulation. Therefore, it
79 is important to understand the pH-dependent regulation of the mechanisms underlying
80 chemotaxis in order to open opportunities to new therapeutic targets or optimize
81 existing ones.

82 Neutrophil chemotaxis is initiated by end-target chemoattractants like complement
83 molecule C5a and formylated peptides, which are secreted at the site of inflammation
84 and employ mainly p38/MAPK pathway in neutrophils. Once activated, the neutrophils
85 themselves release intermediary chemoattractants such as leukotriene B₄ (LTB₄) or
86 IL-8, which bind to leukotriene B₄ or IL-8 receptor (BLT1 and IL-8R, respectively) and
87 act via the PI3K/Akt pathway, boosting immune response in auto- and paracrine ways
88 (11, 12). There is a close interrelation between end-target and intermediary
89 chemoattractants, which can be exemplified by the C5a-LTB₄-BLT1 axis. C5a-
90 stimulated neutrophils release LTB₄ and thereby reinforce chemotaxis and cause
91 neutrophil swarming towards the inflamed site or injured tissue. This “relay”
92 mechanism is essential for proper neutrophil chemotaxis (13, 14).

93 The way in which pH affects neutrophil chemotaxis could manifest itself in a disruption
94 of the C5a-LTB₄-BLT1 axis and consequently altered activation of downstream
95 effectors such as Cdc42. This would lead to a pH-dependence of chemotaxis since
96 Cdc42 regulates neutrophil polarization, actin polymerization and C5a receptor
97 internalization (15, 16, 17, 18). In dendritic cells, inhibition of BLT1 signaling disrupts
98 Cdc42 activation and actin polymerization (19). However, BLT1-Cdc42 interaction and
99 its pH-dependence have not yet been investigated in neutrophils. Since neutrophil
100 migration in a 3D environment relies on actin rearrangements (20) it is possible that a
101 pH-dependent modulation of Cdc42 activity will also affect neutrophil motility.

102 We show in our studies that chemotaxis of C5a-stimulated neutrophils in a 3D collagen
103 matrix is indeed strongly pH- and NHE1-dependent. Our results suggest that the
104 inhibition of neutrophil chemotaxis towards C5a by the extracellular acidity can be
105 explained by a pH-dependently reduced LTB₄ secretion and impaired Cdc42 signaling.
106 Thus, the extracellular acidity or NHE1 inhibition causes an intracellular acidification
107 that in turn is responsible for the observed inhibition of chemotaxis.

108 **2 Materials and Methods**

109 All chemicals were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich, Germany if not stated otherwise.

110 **2.1 Mice**

111 Wild type C57BL/6J male mice (Charles River) were used for all experiments and at
112 least N = 3 mice were used for each condition. Animals were euthanized by cervical
113 dislocation. Experimental protocols were approved by the local committee for animal
114 care with permit number: 84-02.05.50.15.010.

115 **2.2 WEHI-3B conditioned medium**

116 Myelomonocytic leukemia cells (WEHI-3B) were cultivated at 37°C and 5% CO₂ in
117 DMEM medium containing 10% FCS (heat inactivated), 2 mM L-glutamine and 1%
118 penicillin/streptomycin. The cells were cultured for 5 days. Conditioned medium was
119 then collected, sterile filtered and stored at -20°C for later use.

120 **2.3 Isolation of neutrophils**

121 Neutrophils were isolated from murine bone marrow as described earlier (21). In brief,
122 tibia and femur were flushed with Hanks Balanced Salt Solution without Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺
123 ions (HBSS^{-/-}, Merck Chemicals GmbH, Germany) containing 10% FCS
124 (Gibco/ThermoFisher Scientific, Germany) and 25 mM HEPES (pH7.2). The resulting
125 suspension was filtered through a 70 µm nylon mesh and centrifuged at 200 g for 10
126 min. The cell pellet was resuspended in 1 ml HBSS^{-/-} with 25 mM HEPES, gently
127 layered on top of a density gradient (1.077 g/ml and 1.119g/ml Pancoll, PAN-Biotech,
128 Germany) and centrifuged at 677 g for 30 min. Collected neutrophils were washed twice
129 with HBSS^{-/-} containing 10% FCS and 25 mM HEPES and centrifuged at 200 g for 10
130 min. The neutrophils were then resuspended in RPMI1640 medium containing 1%

131 penicillin/streptomycin, 5% heat-inactivated FCS and 5% WEHI-3B-conditioned
132 medium. Cells were cultured overnight at 37 °C, 5 % CO₂ in a Ø10 cm Petri dish. The
133 purity of neutrophil preparations was analyzed by immunocytochemistry using a FITC
134 anti-mouse Ly-6G antibody (clone 1A8, BioLegend, USA). Ly-6G⁺ cells comprised
135 ~85% of nucleated cells.

136 **2.4 Flow cytometry analysis of cell viability**

137 A propidium iodide (PI) flow cytometric assay was performed to determine the viability
138 of the cells. Neutrophils were centrifuged and resuspended in Ringer's solution (140
139 mM NaCl, 5.4 mM KCl, 1.2 mM CaCl₂, 0.8 mM MgCl₂, 10 mM HEPES, 5.5 mM
140 glucose; adjusted to pH_e6.5 or pH_e7.4) after overnight incubation. Then neutrophils
141 were stimulated with 60 nM C5a with or without 10 µM zileuton and incubated for one
142 hour at 37°C. After centrifugation, cells were resuspended in 10 µg/ml propidium iodide
143 in phosphate-buffered saline with 1 mM Ca²⁺ 1 mM and Mg²⁺ ions, containing 0.1 %
144 albumin. Cells were analyzed using Guava easyCyte 5 flow cytometer (Milipore, USA).
145 Following doublet discrimination cells were gated for PI positive cells (PI⁺) based on
146 unstained control samples.

147 **2.5 3D-chemotaxis assay in varied extracellular pH**

148 Chemotaxis was monitored in µ-Slides Chemotaxis (Cat.No: 80326, Ibidi, Germany).
149 Neutrophils were used after 16h of overnight differentiation. The surface of the
150 chemotaxis channel was coated with 25 µg/ml fibronectin (Roche Diagnostics GmbH,
151 Germany) for 1h. Neutrophils were suspended in HEPES-buffered Ringer's solution
152 (pH7.4). Then cells were mixed with collagen I (rat tail, final concentration 2.5 mg/ml,
153 Corning, USA) in Hanks Balanced Salt Solution containing 1 mM Ca²⁺ and 1 mM Mg²⁺
154 (HBSS^{+/+}) buffered with HEPES (25 mM) and adjusted to the desired pH value. When

155 needed this mixture was supplemented with the respective inhibitors. The final
156 concentrations are given in parenthesis: NHE1 inhibitor cariporide (10 μ M), 5-
157 lipoxygenase inhibitor zileuton (10 μ M), BLT1 blocker LY223982 (10 μ M; Cayman
158 Chemical, USA).

159 The chemotaxis channel was filled with the collagen mixture containing 2×10^5
160 neutrophils and incubated at room temperature for 10 min. Afterwards the chambers
161 were filled with HEPES-buffered Ringer's solution of the desired pH value, and the
162 chemoattractant (C5a; 60 nM, R&D Systems, Germany) was added to one of the
163 chambers to create a chemotactic gradient. The optimal C5a concentration (60 nM) for
164 chemotaxis was established by comparing concentrations of 6 nM, 60 nM and 370 nM
165 C5a (see Supplemental Material Figures S1A & B).

166 Migrating cells were observed under a phase contrast microscope (Axiovert 40; Zeiss;
167 Germany) connected to a camera (XC-77CE Hamamatsu, Japan or Bresser MikroCam
168 SP 3.1, Germany). Images were acquired in 5 s intervals for 30 min. The recording
169 started 20 min after establishing the chemoattractant gradient. Pilot experiments had
170 shown that the chemotaxis index of neutrophils is stable after that time. The movement
171 was tracked with Amira software (3D Visualization Sciences Group). Segmented image
172 stacks were processed using the ImageJ software (<https://imagej.nih.gov/ij/>) and a self-
173 made plugin (22). Chemotaxis was quantified with the following parameters: velocity
174 calculated as a three-point difference quotient; total distance covered during the course
175 of the experiment and net movement parallel to the direction of the chemotactic
176 gradient. The chemotactic index (CI) is calculated for each cell by dividing the net
177 movement into the direction of the chemotactic gradient by the total distance.

178 **2.6 3D-chemotaxis in a pH gradient (pH-taxis)**

179 For monitoring 3D chemotaxis in a pH gradient (pH-taxis), the chambers were filled
180 with HEPES-buffered Ringer's solutions adjusted to pH8.0 and pH4.5, respectively.
181 This results in a pH gradient within the collagen matrix ranging from pH7.45 to pH7.2
182 as quantitatively assessed using 2',7'-bis(carboxyethyl)-5(6)-carboxyfluorescein
183 (BCECF) acid as extracellular pH indicator. To this end the 3D collagen matrix
184 containing 5 µg/ml BCECF was loaded into µ-Slides Chemotaxis and fluorescence
185 emission intensities at 535nm upon excitation at 480nm and 440nm were measured
186 across the chemotaxis channel. These measurements were calibrated separately using
187 identical µ-Slides Chemotaxis filled with BCECF-containing collagen matrix adjusted
188 either to pH6.5 or to pH7.4, respectively. Absolute values of the established pH-
189 gradient were calculated from a linear regression based on the ratio of intensities (ex.
190 480nm/440nm) in matrices of known pH. Image acquisition and data analysis were
191 performed in the same way as described above (2.5: 3D chemotaxis assay).

192 **2.7 Determination of the LTB₄ concentration**

193 We determined the concentration of leukotriene B₄ (LTB₄) in the supernatant of
194 neutrophils (10⁶/0.5 ml) kept in HEPES-buffered Ringer's solution of different pH
195 values (pH6.5-7.4) using the LTB₄ Parameter ELISA Assay Kit (R&D Systems,
196 Germany). The cells were stimulated with 60 nM C5a and incubated for one hour at
197 37°C. The supernatant was collected after centrifugation and further processed
198 according to the manufacturer's instructions. The kit provides a standard solution which
199 allows calibration. We performed two technical duplicates for each measurement. The
200 absorbance of the resulting reaction solution was measured at 500 nm in the
201 THERMOmax Microplate Reader (Molecular Devices, USA). The inhibitory efficacy

202 of zileuton was determined by incubating C5a-stimulated cells with 0.1 μ M, 0.3 μ M,
203 1 μ M, 10 μ M and 30 μ M of zileuton. Maximal inhibition of LTB₄ production was
204 reached at a zileuton concentration of 10 μ M (see Supplemental Material Figure S2).

205 **2.8 Determination of the intracellular pH**

206 Intracellular pH (pH_i) was measured using the acetoxymethyl ester of BCECF (BCECF-
207 AM) (ThermoFisher Scientific, USA). The acetoxymethyl form of the pH indicator can
208 freely diffuse into the cytosol where it becomes charged upon hydrolysis and
209 consequently trapped inside the cell. Neutrophils were seeded on fibronectin-coated
210 (25 μ g/ml) Ibidi Slides I (Cat.No: 80106) and loaded with BCECF-AM (2.5 μ g/ml) for 3
211 min at 37°C. Then, slides were washed with HEPES-buffered Ringer's solution and put
212 under the superfusion system mounted to the fluorescence microscope. Image
213 acquisition was controlled by VisiView software (Visitron System, Germany).
214 Fluorescence emission intensities of the separate cells in the field of view were
215 measured at 535 nm with excitation at 480 nm and 440 nm. Each measurement was
216 followed by superfusion with K⁺-rich calibration solutions (125 mM KCl, 1 mM CaCl₂,
217 1 mM MgCl₂, 20 mM HEPES; adjusted to pH6.5, 7.0, 7.5, 7.8) containing 10 μ M
218 nigericin. After background subtraction, absolute pH values were calculated
219 ratiometrically (480nm/440nm) and based on linear regression of intensity ratios of
220 calibration solutions. Separate analysis and calibration were done for each cell.

221 **2.9 NH₄⁺ pre-pulse method for assessing NHE1 activity**

222 The activity of NHE1 was determined using the previously described NH₄⁺ pre-pulse
223 (or acid loading) method (23, 24). Shortly, cells were superfused with a solution
224 containing NH₄Cl (102.5 mM NMDG-HCl, 20 mM NH₄Cl, 5.4 mM KCl, 1.2 mM
225 CaCl₂, 0.8 mM MgCl₂, 1 mM BaCl₂, 10 mM HEPES, 5.5 mM glucose) which

226 dissociates to cell-permeable NH_3 . After entering the cell, NH_3 binds to protons causing
227 an intracellular alkalinization. Subsequent exchange to a Na^+ - and NH_4^+ -free solution
228 (122.5 mM NMDG-HCl, 20 mM NH_4Cl , 5.4 mM KCl, 1.2 mM CaCl_2 , 0.8 mM MgCl_2 ,
229 10 mM HEPES, 5.5 mM glucose) causes the dissociation of NH_4^+ and NH_3 diffusion
230 out of the cell. Rapid accumulation of H^+ occurs due to inhibition of the NHE1 in the
231 absence of Na^+ . The speed of pH_i recovery ($\Delta\text{pH}/\text{min}$) upon readdition of extracellular
232 Na^+ is a measure of NHE1 activity. The contribution of NHE1 to pH recovery was
233 further assessed by supplementing the Na^+ containing HEPES Ringer's solution with 10
234 μM cariporide.

235 **2.10 Cdc42-GTP pull-down and Western blotting**

236 Cdc42 activity in neutrophils was quantified using the Cdc42 Activation Assay
237 Biochem Kit (Cytoskeleton, Inc., USA). The total Cdc42 was compared to the active,
238 GTP-bound form. Prior to C5a stimulation neutrophils were equilibrated at 37°C in
239 Ringer's solution of the desired pH_e value for 10 min. Neutrophils were stimulated with
240 60 nM C5a in Ringer's solution at $\text{pH}6.5$ and $\text{pH}7.4$ for 1 min. Alternatively, neutrophils
241 were stimulated with 60 nM C5a in Ringer's solution at $\text{pH}_e6.5$ and $\text{pH}_e7.4$ for 20 min.
242 When performing experiments with NHE1 inhibition neutrophils were either stimulated
243 with 60 nM C5a in presence of 10 μM cariporide at 37°C for 1 min or firstly incubated
244 with 10 μM cariporide at 37°C for 10 min and then stimulated with 60 nM C5a for 1
245 min. Cells were lysed in lysis buffer containing protease inhibitors provided by the
246 manufacturer. In order to achieve the required protein concentration lysates of
247 neutrophils from 2-3 mice were pooled for each experiment. Equal loading was ensured
248 by measuring the protein concentration of the samples with a Pierce™ BCA Protein
249 Assay Kit (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA). The individual steps of the pull-down assay

250 were performed according to the manufacturer's instructions with some modifications.
251 Following pull-down total protein and corresponding precipitates were loaded onto a
252 10% polyacrylamide gel. GTP γ S-treated lysates served as positive controls. The
253 membrane was incubated overnight with a 1:250 dilution of anti-Cdc42 primary
254 antibody (mouse, clone 4B3) at 4°C. The membrane was further incubated with the
255 goat-anti-mouse HRP antibody (1:25,000) for 1 h at room temperature. The signal was
256 detected using Super Signal West Femto (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA) and
257 chemiluminescence intensities were compared using Image Lab Software Version 6.1
258 (Bio-Rad Laboratories, Inc., USA). Background-subtracted intensities resulting from
259 precipitated Cdc42 protein were set in relation to that of total Cdc42 protein.

260 **2.11 Statistical analysis**

261 All values are given as mean \pm SEM unless indicated otherwise. For comparison
262 between two groups, unpaired Student's t-test was used for normally distributed or
263 Mann-Whitney for non-normally distributed data. More than two groups were compared
264 with one-way ANOVA with Tuckey post-hoc or Kruskal-Wallis with Dunn's post-hoc
265 test. Upper case "N" indicates the number of mice used in the experiments whereas
266 lower case "n" indicates the number of single cells analyzed. $p < 0.05$ was considered
267 statistically significant (*). Analyses were performed with GraphPad Prism version
268 8.3.1 for Windows (GraphPad Software, USA, www.graphpad.com) and R
269 programming language (version 4.0.3; <https://www.R-project.org/>).

270

271

272 **3 Results**

273 **3.1 Neutrophil chemotaxis in a C5a gradient is pH-dependent and** 274 **requires NHE1 activity**

275 The ability of neutrophils to navigate towards an inflamed site is affected by the
276 changing environment. In our studies, we analyzed neutrophil chemotaxis and NHE1
277 activity in a pH range from $\text{pH}_{\text{e}}6.5$ to $\text{pH}_{\text{e}}7.4$. Pilot experiments had shown that
278 chemotaxis is optimal with 60 nM C5a (see Supplemental Material Figure S1A & B).
279 Neutrophil chemotaxis towards C5a is clearly dependent on the ambient pH value and
280 on NHE1 activity. Figure 1A shows the trajectories of individual neutrophils migrating
281 in 3D collagen I gels and monitored for 30 min. Tracks are normalized to common
282 starting points on the y-axis which is in parallel to the chemotactic C5a gradient (grey
283 bar). Neutrophils were exposed to $\text{pH}_{\text{e}}6.5$, 6.8, 7.0 and 7.4. The lower panel illustrates
284 trajectories of neutrophils upon NHE1 inhibition, and Figure 1B and C provide the
285 summary of neutrophil chemotaxis and velocity, respectively. It becomes clearly
286 evident that the chemotaxis index (CI) in a range from $\text{pH}_{\text{e}}6.5$ to $\text{pH}_{\text{e}}7.4$ has a bell-
287 shaped pH-dependence with an optimum at $\text{pH}_{\text{e}}7.0$. Importantly, neutrophil viability
288 does not decrease in pH_{e} as low as $\text{pH}6.5$ as quantified by flow cytometry (see
289 Supplemental Material Figure S3). NHE1 inhibition leads to a massive decrease of
290 neutrophil chemotaxis at $\text{pH}_{\text{e}}7.0$ and $\text{pH}_{\text{e}}7.4$ (at $\text{pH}_{\text{e}}7.4$ by about 75%). At lower pH_{e} ,
291 NHE1 inhibition evokes almost no further inhibition of the already impaired
292 chemotaxis.

293 Neutrophil velocity is also affected by the extracellular pH. However, relative changes
294 of this parameter are not as pronounced as those of the chemotaxis index. An
295 extracellular acidification to $\text{pH}_{\text{e}}6.5$ induces a reduction of the velocity by ~25%. In

296 contrast to neutrophil directionality, the ability of neutrophils to roam the acidic
297 environment, although diminished, is largely preserved. The simultaneous inhibition of
298 the NHE1 leads to a further decrease of the velocity by an additional 10-20% for each of
299 the tested pH_e values. Taken together, these results indicate that neutrophil chemotaxis
300 (directionality) rather than the migration motor (velocity) is particularly dependent on
301 the "correct" ambient H^+ concentration and NHE1 activity.

302 **3.2 A pH_e -gradient induces moderate directional migration of** 303 **neutrophils and strengthens the effect of a C5a gradient**

304 In the next set of experiments, we studied the impact of a pH_e gradient *per se* (from
305 $\text{pH}_e 7.2$ to $\text{pH}_e 7.45$) and its combination with a C5a gradient (60 nM C5a) on neutrophil
306 chemotaxis. This allowed us to mimic *in vivo* conditions in which inflammation is a
307 source of both protons and chemoattractants. When investigating the effect of a proton
308 gradient *per se*, we analyzed the movement of neutrophils from three horizontal sections
309 (I, II, III) of the visual field separately (Figure 2A). However, when studying the
310 combined effect of a proton and a C5a gradient, we had to divide the field of view into
311 two horizontal sections (I, II, Figure 2B) because C5a-stimulated neutrophils cover
312 longer net distances during the course of the experiment. By analyzing neutrophils
313 residing in spatially distinct sections separately, we could link neutrophil chemotaxis to
314 a range of pH_e values within the pH_e gradient. When no pH_e gradient was imposed
315 (upper panel Figure 2C), all neutrophils were exposed to $\text{pH}_e 7.4$.

316 The pH_e gradient alone induces moderate neutrophil directionality in sections II and III
317 ($\text{CI} \sim 0.05$; $p < 0.05$). In the most acidic section (I, $\sim \text{pH}_e 7.2$) neutrophils migrate in a
318 random fashion ($\text{CI} \sim 0$) (Figure 2A). As expected, addition of C5a induces efficient

319 chemotaxis (Figure 2B). When applying the same analysis algorithm for the two
320 sections I and II, the mean chemotaxis index does not differ. However, analysis of
321 chemotaxis *over the time* reveals that the chemotaxis index of C5a-stimulated
322 neutrophils steadily increases in the more acidic section (Figure 2C, lower graph). This
323 is not the case for those cells that reside in the more alkaline half of the pH_e gradient.
324 Thus, the combination of a chemoattractant (C5a) and shallow H^+ gradient amplifies the
325 chemotactic response. Such a behavior is not observed in the absence of a pH_e gradient
326 (Figure 2C, upper graph). Regardless of the spatial position within the visual field
327 chemotaxis towards C5a alone (i.e. in the absence of an additional pH gradient) reaches
328 an optimum after ~20 min and declines thereafter. Collectively, our results show that a
329 pH_e gradient approaching $\text{pH}_e 7.2$ favors neutrophil chemotaxis. Thus, as opposed to *A.*
330 *proteus* (25) an extracellular proton gradient is rather a modulator of neutrophil
331 chemotaxis than a strong chemoattractant itself.

332 **3.3 NHE1 determines pH_i dynamics of stimulated neutrophils**

333 Neutrophils arriving at the site of inflammation are influenced by both acidic pH and
334 abundant chemoattractants. To assess the impact of the acidic environment on
335 neutrophil pH_i , we firstly measured pH_i while superfusing the cells with HEPES-
336 buffered Ringer's solution adjusted to $\text{pH}_e 6.5$ (Figure 3A). The change from the
337 physiological $\text{pH}_e 7.4$ to the acidic $\text{pH}_e 6.5$ leads to a slow decrease of the cytoplasmic
338 pH_i of neutrophils that reaches a plateau at $\text{pH}_i 6.90 \pm 0.04$ within 5 min.

339 Next, we examined the combined effect of an extracellular acidification and the
340 stimulation with C5a on pH_i . To dissect the changes of neutrophil pH_i in varied pH_e
341 upon C5a stimulation, we preincubated the cells in HEPES-buffered Ringer's solution at

342 pH_e 6.5, 7.0 and 7.4 for ~10 min and then added C5a (Figure 3B). To assess the role of
343 NHE1 in neutrophil stimulation in solutions of different pH_e , we additionally conducted
344 these measurements in the presence of 10 μM cariporide.

345 As shown in Figure 3A, the pH_i of neutrophils depends on the extracellular pH. When
346 kept in acidic pH_e , the pH_i follows, but does not exactly reach the value of the
347 extracellular pH. This is illustrated by the distinct starting points of each curve in Figure
348 3B. Stimulation with C5a (solid lines) causes a drop of pH_i . At pH_e 6.5 the pH_i decrease
349 develops more slowly. Additional inhibition of NHE1 (dashed lines) strongly amplifies
350 the C5a-induced acidification of the pH_i in neutrophils. Thus, pH_i of C5a-stimulated
351 neutrophils not only depends on the ambient pH_e , but is also importantly regulated by
352 NHE1.

353 We finally demonstrated NHE1 activity in neutrophil pH_i regulation by means of the
354 ammonium pre-pulse technique. Following an intracellular acidification pH_i rapidly
355 recovers in a Na^+ -dependent and cariporide-inhibitable way (Figure 4A). The
356 differences of the rate of pH_i changes within 1 min of Na^+ readdition relate to the NHE1
357 involvement in pH_i recovery (Figure 4B).

358 **3.4 LTB₄ release depends on pH_e**

359 Leukotriene B₄ (LTB₄) plays a major role in neutrophil chemotaxis in a C5a gradient
360 (14, 26). We therefore tested whether the secretion of LTB₄ is pH-dependent. To this
361 end we quantified LTB₄ in the supernatant of neutrophils stimulated with 60 nM C5a
362 using an ELISA assay. To validate the assay and confirm increased LTB₄ production
363 upon stimulation we performed control experiments (at pH_e 7.41 ± 0.07) without and
364 with C5a. Unstimulated neutrophils produce negligible amounts of LTB₄ (below the

365 sensitivity of the assay), whereas C5a stimulation leads to a substantial increase of the
366 LTB₄ concentration in the supernatant. Addition of zileuton (5-LOX inhibitor; 0.1 μM,
367 0.3 μM, 1 μM, 10 μM and 30 μM) to stimulated neutrophils abrogates this response
368 dose-dependently (see Supplemental Material Figure S2).

369 Next, we determined in detail the pH-dependence of the LTB₄ secretion of C5a-
370 stimulated neutrophils. Figure 5A illustrates that the secretion rate is highest at pH_e7.11
371 ± 0.06 and only declines slightly upon acidification to pH_e6.91 ± 0.05 (-8.9 %).
372 However, LTB₄ secretion drops sharply when pH_e is further lowered to pH_e6.67 ± 0.05
373 or increased to pH_e7.41 ± 0.07. Addition of the NHE1 inhibitor cariporide modifies the
374 pH_e-dependency of LTB₄ production. Surprisingly, cariporide enhances LTB₄ secretion
375 at pH_e7.4 (Figure 5B, C).

376 In Figure 6, pH-dependent LTB₄ release and chemotaxis are plotted as a function of the
377 respective extracellular pH. It is evident that the LTB₄ secretion has a similar pH_e-
378 dependence as the chemotaxis under control conditions with the optimum at pH_e7.1
379 (Figure 6A). However, addition of cariporide disrupts this parallel behavior leading to
380 the highest LTB₄ production at pH_e7.4, while neutrophil chemotaxis is severely
381 inhibited (Figure 6B, C).

382 Importantly, as shown in Figure 3, pH_e affects pH_i and in this manner may alter the
383 intracellular processes. Therefore, we analysed the LTB₄ production and chemotaxis as
384 a function of pH_i. The same relation as with pH_e becomes apparent when LTB₄
385 production is compared with the intracellular pH_i (Figure 7A). The increase of the LTB₄
386 production in the presence of cariporide at pH_e7.4 can be explained by the fact that the
387 resulting intracellular pH of pH_i7.1 corresponds to the optimal pH_i for LTB₄ production

388 under control conditions. Thus, NHE1 inhibition shifts the maximum LTB₄ secretion to
389 more alkaline pH_e values (Figure 7A). Nonetheless, chemotaxis is almost completely
390 inhibited in the presence of cariporide at pH_i7.1 (Figure B, C). These observations
391 strongly support an apparently obligatory role of NHE1 for chemotaxis. Its inhibition is
392 able to override increased LTB₄ release. As shown below, cariporide impairs
393 chemotaxis almost as efficiently as interfering with the LTB₄/BLT1 axis directly.

394 **3.5 Neutrophil chemotaxis is suppressed by interfering with the** 395 **LTB₄/BLT1 axis**

396 The superimposition of chemotaxis indices and LTB₄ secretion (Figure 6) suggests that
397 the reduced LTB₄ secretion may be causally linked to the pH-dependent impairment of
398 the chemotaxis. Therefore, we investigated the chemotactic behavior in a C5a gradient
399 upon direct inhibition of the LTB₄/BLT1 axis. We inhibited either the production of
400 LTB₄ using the 5-LOX inhibitor zileuton (10 μM) or blocked the LTB₄ receptor B1
401 (BLT1) with LY223982 (10 μM). As shown earlier (27), blocking the LTB₄ production
402 or its receptor (almost) completely inhibits neutrophil chemotaxis. Figure 8A shows the
403 respective trajectories of neutrophils recorded at pH_e7.0. The summary of these
404 experiments is depicted in Figure 8B and 8C. Both drugs, which are equally effective,
405 strongly reduce the chemotaxis index and the migration velocity. It is conspicuous that
406 the chemotaxis index declines even more than the velocity. However, the strong
407 interference with the LTB₄/BLT1 axis overrides the pH_e-dependence so that any
408 residual pH_e-dependence of neutrophil chemotaxis and migration cannot be interpreted
409 with certainty.

410 **3.6 Cdc42 activation is inhibited by cariporide and an acidic pH_e**

411 Cdc42 is a member of Rho GTPases involved in neutrophil motility. The active Cdc42-

412 GTP form is required for actin rearrangements at the leading edge of neutrophils,
413 neutrophil polarization and consequently proper chemotaxis (18). This is particularly
414 relevant for neutrophils migrating in a 3D environment, which prioritizes the actin-
415 based motility over the integrin-based motility on a 2D surface (20). The former
416 becomes essential once neutrophils extravasate and travel through the tissue. Our results
417 reveal diminished neutrophil chemotaxis in a 3D matrix in the presence of the NHE1
418 blocker cariporide and at $\text{pH}_e 6.5$. Therefore, we aimed at elucidating whether this could
419 be due to a reduced amount of activated Cdc42-GTP. Cdc42 activity was determined at
420 two time points following C5a stimulation: after 1 min and after 20 min. Our results
421 reveal that Cdc42 activity in neutrophils is indeed NHE1- and pH-dependent. Notably,
422 Cdc42 activity is much higher at the early time point. However, regardless of the
423 absolute value, there is always a ~60% decrease in the Cdc42-GTP/Cdc42 ratio upon
424 NHE1 inhibition and at $\text{pH}_e 6.5$, respectively (Figure 9A, B). Interestingly, Cdc42
425 activity is not inhibited when neutrophils are stimulated with C5a in the presence of
426 cariporide for only 1 min without prior incubation with the NHE1 inhibitor
427 (Supplemental Material Figure S4). This observation provides an additional explanation
428 that the observed impairment of neutrophil chemotaxis upon NHE1 inhibition and
429 reduced pH_e both act on Cdc42 activity via an intracellular acidification. We have
430 shown in Figure 3 that 1 min in $\text{pH}_e 6.5$ or 1 min of NHE1 inhibition is not sufficient to
431 change pH_i significantly.

432

433 **4 Discussion**

434 Tissue acidification affects neutrophil chemotaxis in a distinct way. Chemotaxis has an
435 optimum at a slightly acidic pH_e 7.0 and lowering or increasing the pH_e to pH_e 6.8 or
436 pH_e 7.4 has little effect. Supporting our observations, chemotactic efficiency in a C5a
437 gradient is augmented when neutrophils are simultaneously exposed to an equally
438 aligned extracellular proton gradient approaching the optimal pH_e . Such a pH_e gradient
439 can be encountered by neutrophils in the interstitium after extravasation. Further
440 decreasing pH_e to pH_e 6.5 strongly impairs chemotaxis, but neutrophil velocity, a
441 surrogate of the migration motor, is changed to a much lesser extent by variations of the
442 extracellular pH. This suggests that neutrophils chemotax less efficiently once they
443 reach an acidic site of inflammation, but retain their migratory abilities.

444 Mechanistically, our results indicate that alterations of pH_i play a decisive role in
445 mediating the effects of an extracellular acidification or NHE1 inhibition. In our view
446 pH_i is a major determinant of the two pH-dependent mechanisms identified in this
447 study: pH-dependent LTB_4 release and Cdc42 activity are major causes of the pH-
448 dependence of chemotaxis. C5a-stimulated neutrophils release the maximum amount of
449 LTB_4 at pH_e 7.0 and its release is greatly reduced at pH_e 6.5. This apparent pH_e
450 dependence of the LTB_4 release mirrors that of chemotaxis. However, during the course
451 of our experiments it became evident that it is rather the *intracellular* than the
452 extracellular pH, which affects LTB_4 release. Lowering the pH_i by inhibiting NHE1 at
453 an extracellular pH_e 7.4 leads to a seemingly paradoxical increase of the LTB_4 release
454 because the intracellular pH shifts to the optimal value for LTB_4 release.

455 So far, it has not yet been studied whether an acidic pH_e or pH_i influence exosomal or
456 intracellular LTB_4 -producing enzymes. However, an indirect pH-dependent modulation

457 of the LTB₄ production is also possible. One of the key enzymes of the LTB₄
458 production cascade, cPLA₂, is stimulated by an increase of the intracellular Ca²⁺
459 concentration ([Ca²⁺]_i) (28). Such an increase of the [Ca²⁺]_i is induced by C5a, which is
460 at least in part mediated by the activation of Orai1 (29). Orai1, in turn, is inhibited by an
461 extra- and intracellular acidification (30, 31). Thus, an inhibition of Orai1 by an
462 acidification is expected to lead to a pH-dependent reduction of the LTB₄ production.

463 It is unknown whether the process of exosome secretion by neutrophils is pH-
464 dependent. Interestingly, it was shown that exosome release from carcinoma cells of
465 different tumor entities appears to be regulated in the opposite way. It is increased in an
466 acidic environment (32). We are aware that the nature of cancer cell-derived exosomes
467 may not be the same as those from neutrophils. Nonetheless, the observations made in
468 cancer cells cannot explain our findings of the reduced LTB₄ concentration in an acidic
469 supernatant. The observations made in cancer cells would rather argue for an increased
470 production of LTB₄ in neutrophils when pH_e is lowered. Undoubtedly, more studies are
471 needed to clarify this question.

472 Also, the fact that neutrophils may influence the local pericellular pH via exocytosis of
473 acidic vesicles and NHE1 activity can be of importance in the context of neutrophil
474 chemotaxis. Although we did not observe measurable pH changes in the cell matrix
475 upon C5a stimulation, we cannot dismiss the possibility that local pH disturbances may
476 influence other neutrophils migrating in the proximity or modify cell-matrix
477 interactions. We had shown previously that the pericellular pH_e within the glycocalyx
478 regulates migration of melanoma cells NHE1-dependently by controlling β1-integrin
479 mediated cell-matrix adhesion (33, 34). However, such a mechanism is unlikely to
480 account for the observed pH-dependence of neutrophil chemotaxis because neutrophil

481 migration in a 3D environment is integrin-independent (20, 35). We therefore propose
482 that the intracellular pH is more important for regulating neutrophil chemotaxis in a 3D
483 environment than the extracellular pH.

484 A further explanation for the diminished chemotaxis in an acidic pH is given by the fact
485 that LTB₄ regulates Cdc42 activation. Cdc42 is a member of the small Rho-GTPases
486 family and is crucial for chemotaxis. The role of Cdc42 is underlined by its distribution
487 and asymmetric activation in neutrophil-like PLB-985 cells (18). Hence, the markedly
488 attenuated activation of Cdc42 in an acidic environment is consistent with the impaired
489 chemotaxis efficiency of neutrophils under these conditions. A decrease in LTB₄ release
490 in an acidic pH may directly lead to the diminished Cdc42-GTP level. Since LTB₄ itself
491 mediates an enhancement of neutrophil chemotaxis (13, 15) it likely triggers the
492 activation of Rho GTPases. Further analysis of Cdc42 activation upon LTB₄ stimulation
493 in an acidic pH is required to elucidate this possibility.

494 The expression of the proton sensing G-protein coupled receptors in neutrophils (e.g.
495 OGR1, TDAG8) (36) may also play a role in the observed response of neutrophils. The
496 activation of TDAG8 by an acidic pH leads to an increased cAMP accumulation in
497 neutrophil-like HL-60 and human neutrophils (37). OGR1 also mediates inositol
498 phosphate formation in several cell lines (38). The involvement of these receptors in
499 pH-dependent neutrophil chemotaxis, however, remains elusive.

500 Despite high LTB₄ production in cells treated with the NHE1 inhibitor at physiological
501 pH_e7.4 (pH_i7.05) neutrophil chemotaxis is severely impeded. Here we show that NHE1
502 blockade leads to a reduced activity of Cdc42 in murine neutrophils (previously shown
503 also in fibroblasts (39) and neurite outgrowth (40)). Thus, it is not surprising that NHE1

504 inhibition impairs neutrophil chemotaxis as well. According to our findings, NHE1
505 activity appears to be a prerequisite for chemotaxis towards C5a when pH_i is ~ 7.1 . Yet,
506 the understanding of the mutual regulation of NHE1, pH and Rho-GTPases such as
507 Rho, Rac and Cdc42 is far from being complete. There are only few studies showing
508 that Cdc42, Rac1 or RhoA are regulated by the intracellular pH (39, 40, 41). Thus, we
509 cannot rule out that, in addition to Cdc42, the other Rho-GTPases, in particular Rac1,
510 also contribute to pH-dependent neutrophil chemotaxis. RhoA, the major Rho isoform
511 in neutrophils, appears to be an unlikely candidate to account for the inhibition of
512 chemotaxis in an acidic environment. RhoA deletion is accompanied by a
513 hyperactivation of neutrophils (42). Finally, we cannot dismiss the possibility that the
514 effect of pH on small GTPases could be an indirect one: The Ras-specific guanine
515 nucleotide exchange factor RasGRP1 is pH-sensitive and would thereby control Ras
516 activity in a pH-dependent manner (43). However, at least in A431 cells Tiam1, Vav2,
517 and Dock180 that have been implicated in epidermal growth factor receptor-mediated
518 activation of Rac1 and Cdc42 were not affected by changes of pH_i (41).

519 What is the pathophysiological implication of our findings? The results of our pH-taxis
520 experiments indicate that extravasation of stimulated neutrophils is possibly accelerated
521 by a shallow proton gradient. Along these lines, both pH of the blood and interstitial pH
522 are relevant factors for the recruitment of stimulated neutrophils. Our results also
523 indicate that neutrophil chemotaxis is impaired in the acidic inflammatory
524 microenvironment while the velocity is reduced only to a minor extent. This
525 corroborates results from *in vivo* studies showing increased neutrophil directionality at
526 the periphery of the injury and rather random motility closer to the insult core (44). We
527 propose that an acidic extracellular pH within an inflammatory focus may contribute to

528 this phenomenon. It is known that neutrophils acquire prolonged survival in an acidic
529 environment and that neutrophil killing mechanisms are reinforced (45). Our
530 observations add to this picture the disrupted neutrophil chemotaxis, which will further
531 contribute to neutrophil retention at the site of inflammation.

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840 **Figure 1. Extracellular pH and NHE1 activity predominantly regulate neutrophil**
841 **chemotaxis towards C5a.** (A) Trajectories of individual neutrophils migrating in a 3D
842 collagen I matrix. They are exposed to a C5a gradient in pH_e 6.5, 6.8, 7.0 and 7.4. The
843 direction of the C5a gradient is indicated on the right hand side. The lower panels show
844 the trajectories of neutrophils in the presence of the NHE1 inhibitor cariporide. All
845 trajectories are normalized to common starting points along the y-axis, which represents
846 the direction of the C5a gradient. (B) Chemotaxis indices and (C) velocity of
847 neutrophils migrating in different pH_e environments without (closed bars) and with
848 NHE1 inhibition (open bars) ($N \geq 3$, $n \geq 60$, Kruskal-Wallis, Dunn's post hoc, $*p <$
849 0.05 ; $\#p < 0.05$ vs optimum at pH_e 7.0).

850 **Figure 2. Neutrophil pH-taxis.** (A) Trajectories and pH-taxis indices (left) of
851 neutrophils migrating in a pH_e gradient. The position of the sections I, II and III in the
852 pH gradient are indicated in the pictogram above the trajectories ($*p < 0.05$, compared
853 with 0). (B) Trajectories of C5a-stimulated neutrophils in a pH_e gradient. The position
854 of the sections I and II in the pH gradient are indicated in the pictogram above the
855 trajectories. (C) Comparison of chemotaxis indices of C5a-stimulated neutrophils in the
856 two sections I and II over the time. The upper graph shows chemotaxis over the time
857 when there is no pH gradient. The lower graph depicts chemotaxis towards C5a in a pH_e
858 gradient. Closed and open circles indicate sections closer and further away from the
859 chemoattractant source (control: $N \geq 3$, $n \geq 60$, pH gradient: $N \geq 4$, $n \geq 40$).

860 **Figure 3. Influence of the acidic pH_e , C5a stimulation and NHE1 activity on**
861 **neutrophil pH_i .** (A) pH_i of neutrophils superfused with HEPES-buffered Ringer's
862 solution of pH_e 6.5. Neutrophil pH_i reaches steady values of pH_i 6.90 ± 0.04 after
863 approximately 5 min. (B) Solid curves represent pH_i changes of neutrophils kept in a
864 range of distinct pH_e values and stimulated with C5a. Dashed lines depict experiments
865 with addition of the NHE1 inhibitor cariporide ($N \geq 3$, $n \geq 40-102$).

866 **Figure 4. Neutrophil pH_i recovery after acidification (ammonium pre-pulse)**
867 **without or with NHE1 inhibition.** (A) pH_i of neutrophils superfused with Na^+ -
868 containing HEPES-buffered Ringer's solution (control, filled circles) and upon
869 inhibition of NHE1 with cariporide (10 μM ; open circles). (B) Summary of the pH_i
870 recovery rates within 1 min under control conditions and in the presence of the NHE1

871 inhibitor cariporide ($N \geq 4$, $n \geq 76-111$).

872 **Figure 5. LTB₄ secretion depends on pH_e and NHE1 activity.** Each dotted line
873 connects measurements with neutrophils from the same mouse. The mean values for
874 each condition are indicated in black. (A) The LTB₄ concentration in supernatants of
875 neutrophils stimulated with 60 nM C5a in pH_e ranging from pH_e6.67 to pH_e7.41
876 ($N = 5$). (B) LTB₄ concentration of stimulated neutrophils upon NHE1 inhibition. ($N \geq$
877 3) (p values determined using ANOVA with Dunett's post-hoc test versus values at
878 pH_e7.11) (C) Comparison between control and cariporide- treated neutrophils. p -value
879 indicates significant difference at pH_e7.4.

880 **Figure 6. LTB₄ release and chemotaxis indices in different pH_e environments.** (A)
881 Chemotaxis index (CI) and pH_e-dependent LTB₄ release under control conditions. (B)
882 Comparison of LTB₄ release and chemotaxis in the presence of the NHE1 inhibitor
883 cariporide. (C) Radar chart summarizing migratory abilities (velocity and chemotaxis)
884 with LTB₄ production in varied pH_e environments. Values measured at pH_e7.0
885 (chemotaxis) and pH_e7.1 (LTB₄ concentration) are taken as 100%.

886 **Figure 7. LTB₄ release and chemotaxis as a function of pH_i.** (A) LTB₄ production in
887 varied pH_i environments without (closed circles) and with cariporide (open circles). (B)
888 Chemotaxis indices in different pH_i environments. (C) Comparison of LTB₄ production
889 and chemotaxis at pH_i7.1 (dissected from A and B, circled) without and with cariporide.

890 **Figure 8. Neutrophil chemotaxis upon LTB₄/BLT1 axis inhibition in different pH_e**
891 **environments** (A) Trajectories of individual neutrophils migrating in a 3D collagen I
892 matrix. Trajectories are normalized to common starting points along the y-axis which
893 corresponds to the direction of the C5a gradient. Its direction is indicated on the right
894 hand side. The left panel shows control experiments at pH_e7.0. The middle and right
895 panels depict chemotaxis at pH_e7.0 in the presence of the 5-LOX inhibitor zileuton and
896 the BLT1 blocker LY223982, respectively. (B) Mean values of the chemotaxis indices
897 and (C) of the velocity at pH_e6.5 – pH_e7.4. In (B) and (C) we compare control values
898 with those in the presence of zileuton or LY223982 ($N \geq 3$, $n \geq 60$, Kruskal-Wallis,
899 Dunn's post hoc test).

900

901 **Figure 9. Cdc42 activation decreases upon NHE1 inhibition and an acidic pH_e.** (A)
902 Pull down experiments showing the amount of the active Cdc42-GTP form in C5a-
903 stimulated neutrophils without and with cariporide. Neutrophils were pretreated with
904 cariporide (10 μM) for 10 min prior to stimulation with C5a for 1 min. A representative
905 immunoblot (upper panel) of one of the three independent experiments. The lower panel
906 shows a summary of the densitometric evaluation (ratios and normalized data) of the
907 immunoblots (N=3 replicates of pooled lysates from 2 mice each). (B) Representative
908 immunoblot (upper panel) and densitometric analysis (ratios and normalized data) of
909 neutrophils stimulated with C5a in pH_e7.4 and pH_e6.5. Neutrophils were preequilibrated
910 at pH_e7.4 or pH_e6.5 for 10 min prior to stimulation with C5a for 1 min (N=3 replicates
911 of pooled lysates from 3 mice each).

912

ApH_e 6.5pH_e 6.8pH_e 7.0pH_e 7.4

C5a

y coordinate (μm)

+ cariporide:

C5a

y coordinate (μm)

A

B

C

A

A

Extracellular pH controls chemotaxis of neutrophil granulocytes by regulating LTB₄ production and Cdc42 signaling

Supplemental Material

Running title: pH regulates neutrophil chemotaxis

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Figure S1. Neutrophil chemotaxis towards C5a. (A) Trajectories of individual neutrophils migrating in a 3D collagen I matrix for 30 min. The C5a gradient is generated with different concentrations of the chemoattractant: 6 nM, 60 nM, 370 nM. The direction of the C5a gradient is indicated on the right hand side. All trajectories are normalized to common starting points along the y-axis, which represents the direction of the C5a gradient. (B) Chemotaxis indices of neutrophils migrating in different C5a gradients (N = 4-5, n = 80-100, * $p < 0.05$).

Figure S2. LTB₄ secretion is inhibited dose-dependently by the 5-LOX inhibitor zileuton. Each dot represents a single measurement. The mean values ± SEM are indicated by horizontal lines. N = 3 with two technical duplicates each.

Figure S3. Viability of neutrophils. Suspended neutrophils were incubated for 1 h in Ringer's solution (pH7.4 or pH6.5) in the absence or presence of 10 μ M zileuton. Thereafter, they were stained with propidium iodide (PI) and the resulting fluorescence was quantified with flow cytometry. **A/B)** Exemplary histograms of PI-stained neutrophils treated with zileuton at pH6.5. **C)** Statistical evaluation of the experiments. Neither the extracellular acidification nor zileuton affect the viability of neutrophils. N = 4.

A

20 min pH and C5a

B

1 min cariporide + C5a

Figure S4. Cdc42 activity depends on the intracellular pH. **A)** A sustained low Cdc42 activity is observed when C5a-stimulated neutrophils are kept in an acidic Ringer's solution (pH_e 6.5) for 20 min. **B)** When neutrophils are exposed to NHE1 inhibitor cariporide for 1 min during a 1min C5a stimulation, Cdc42 activity does not change. 1 min is too short for cariporide to elicit a substantial acidification of the pH_i.